

How to bring innovation and improvement the worldwide SME purchasing and supply chain processes. How can we develop big Aviation players businesses by using the Blockchain.

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

The GSC Aviation Marketplace wants to create a virtuous circle of relationships between purchasers and suppliers globally.

2. Aim

GSC Aviation aims to reduce time in processes and costs for purchasers which will permit them to focus on more value-added tasks for their company. At the same time, it will bring to big European and North American suppliers potential customers from emergent aviation markets such as Middle-East, Africa or Asia.

3. Material and methods

Technical tools dedicated to the purchasers will permit the saving of precious time by providing them with a suppliers follow-up system within their work scope of suppliers. A detailed ID sheet on each supplier will permit buyers to integrate them a lot faster to their supplier portfolio. A e-sourcing module, with spare parts and services provided by referenced suppliers on the GSC Aviation database, will be fitted for all purchasers that the aviation area need to follow in terms of regulations.

A simplified rating system such as on Trip Advisor, will permit the purchasers to give a notation following the RFQ (Request For Quotation) which will enable the suppliers rated to appear on top or on the bottom of the list of the next purchaser RFQ.

On the other side we will also provide a rating system for the suppliers who will give good or poor notation of the purchasers regarding financial solidity, and if invoices are paid on time.

Finally, in parallel of this platform will be created the BC Reverse Auction Marketplace of GSC Aviation based on an ERC20 Token. For huge purchases and investments, big companies will be able to save time and money by letting GSC Aviation take care of the organization of the reverse auction all set by a smart contract.

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4. Results

GSC Aviation is about to create its landing page and MVP website version in order that two of our partners, both CEO's of aviation related companies can test the platform and give us their feedback to make the best product possible.

5. Conclusions

Blockchain Marketplace, Aviation Industry, Improvement of processes, Scale savings, Business development.

6. Keywords

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Author biography

Maxime Legros He has been working in the aerospace sector as a buyer for over 7 years. Curious, strategist, comfortable in relationships, he enjoys teamwork and project management.

Passionate about his job, he has developed skills through experience and has decided to resume his studies at age 33 to pass a professional degree of Industrial Purchaser / Supply Chain Management alternately.